

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF MOBILE APPLICATION TESTING ON IOS AND ANDROID PLATFORMS: IMPACT ON DEVELOPMENT COST AND DIGITAL PRODUCT LIFECYCLE

Drogunova Y.

*Bachelor's degree, Dostoevsky Omsk State University
Russia, Omsk*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16778582>

Abstract

The article examines the impact of architectural differences between iOS and Android platforms on the choice of mobile application testing strategies. It analyzes runtime environments, automation tools, fragmentation levels, and platform-specific maintenance requirements. It is emphasized that the specifics of testing on each platform significantly affect development costs, release timelines, and total cost of ownership. Comparative data are presented on execution time, stability, resource consumption, and test scalability. The study also assesses the effect of platform constraints on the product life cycle, including update, maintenance, and end-of-life stages. The paper concludes that mapping of QA strategies to platform-specific parameters is imperative for cost-effectiveness as well as long-term viability of digital products.

Keywords: testing, mobile applications, Android, iOS, automation, total cost of ownership, product lifecycle.

Introduction

Modern digital products are created increasingly in the shape of mobile applications for different operating systems. The most common platforms remain Android and iOS, both of which make particular technological and organizational requirements for development and testing processes. Due to rising competition, shorter time-to-market, and growing user demands, testing workflow efficiency became a matter of utmost concern. Most relevant are factors related to differences in platform architecture, test tool specificity, and quality assurance expense, as these directly impact both project budgets and the product lifecycle as a whole.

The aim of this study is to conduct comparative analysis of mobile app testing strategies on the Android and iOS platforms on technical and economic grounds. Architectural properties, the test tools and frameworks employed, and time and cost expenditures pertaining to product upkeep and maintenance are compared.

Main part. Architectural differences between iOS and Android platforms

Generally, iOS is generally built on a variant of the **XNU kernel** (where X is Not Unix), which combines the microkernel concept of Mach with aspects of

FreeBSD. Mach handles memory management and process control, while FreeBSD provides the networking stack and POSIX interfaces [1]. There is IOKit in the kernel, which is an object-oriented driver subsystem responsible for monitoring hardware communication.

Above the kernel lies the Core OS layer, which holds low-level libraries such as libSystem and Security, as well as higher-level frameworks such as Core Services, Media, and Cocoa Touch – the latter spanning UIKit and Foundation, which all together set the foundation for user interface building and application behavior.

All applications are executed within a **sandboxed** environment, which enhances system security but restricts access to system-level API. iOS enforces mandatory code signing, Address Space Layout Randomization (ASLR), Data Execution Prevention (DEP), and prohibits Just-In-Time (JIT) compilation, all of which contribute to resistance against common attack vectors. Additionally, the Secure Enclave – a dedicated hardware module – provides enhanced protection for biometric data and cryptographic keys (fig.1).

Figure 1. iOS system architecture overview

The closed architecture of iOS limits the use of third-party frameworks and tools, complicating low-level testing efforts. However, this model ensures system stability, predictability in runtime behavior, and a high level of overall security.

Android, in contrast, is built on an open-source Linux kernel and utilizes the Android Runtime (ART)

virtual machine for application execution [2]. This architecture introduces a higher level of abstraction between the application layer and the underlying hardware, while simultaneously offering developers broader access to system resources (fig.2).

Figure 2. Layered architecture of the Android operating system

Because of the open-source nature of Android Open Source Project (AOSP), there are a huge number of custom OS builds, and a significant ecosystem of OEM devices with differing hardware configurations. It highly increases platform fragmentation. From the test perspective, it needs extensive test coverage on multiple devices, OS versions, and manufacturer-specific user interfaces. Unlike iOS, Android allows the use of high-level logging capabilities, personal firmware, and low-level assets (such as `adb`, `logcat`, and `uiautomator`) to build mature automated test cases yet also complicate compatibility verification.

It also needs to be noted about component lifecycle variations. In Android, the lifecycle of components such as `Activity`, `Fragment`, and `Service` is tightly managed by the system and subject to asynchronous transition of state depending upon whether memory is available or not and what the user does. It is something that must be considered specially while testing UI and simulating user actions. In iOS, view controller lifetimes (`UIViewController`) are more predictable but

are tightly entwined in the user interface hierarchy, affecting navigation testing and event handling strategies.

Thus, the architectural characteristics of each platform define distinct technical requirements for testing strategies. The closed and standardized environment of iOS enables more predictable testing conditions but with limited low-level access. In contrast, the open and fragmented nature of Android demands broader testing coverage and greater flexibility, yet provides a rich set of tools for constructing scalable and comprehensive test frameworks.

Testing tools and frameworks

The choice of automated testing tools for mobile platforms directly impacts the efficiency of quality assurance processes, functional coverage, and the scalability of test suites. Among the most widely adopted frameworks are XCTest (for iOS), Espresso (for Android), as well as cross-platform solutions such as Appium and Detox. These frameworks differ significantly in terms of architecture, test execution models, and the degree of integration with CI/CD pipelines (table 1).

Table 1.

Comparative table of mobile application testing frameworks [3, 4]

Framework	Platform	Key strengths	Key limitations	Technical characteristics
XCTest	iOS	High stability, fast execution, native Xcode integration	iOS-only, requires macOS and Apple accounts.	Compiled with app; uses XCTest API; supports parallel device testing.
Espresso	Android	Stable UI tests, good integration with Android Studio and CI	Android-only, no cross-app test support.	Runs in app process; synchronized API; integrated with Gradle.
Appium	iOS / Android / Windows	Cross-platform, scalable, rich ecosystem	Slower due to WebDriver layer, async issues possible.	WebDriver-based; communicates over HTTP; supports Selenium Grid & Docker,
Detox	iOS / Android (React Native)	Optimized for React Native, sync with event loop	Limited to React Native, setup complexity.	Runs test in Node.js; syncs with native event loop; supports CI pipelines.

Architecturally, iOS and Android impose basically different constraints on test tools. The iOS ecosystem is control- and security-oriented: apps are sandboxed, the OS prevents the execution of unauthorized code, and low-level hooks are prohibited. This reduces flexibility but allows for predictable device behavior. Test frameworks like XCUITest operate at the user interface level and are strongly coupled with the XCTest API and Xcode, making them more stable but strongly coupled with Apple infrastructure. Test runs are limited to macOS environments, which makes CI/CD scaling more complicated and requires the utilization of third-party services like Bitrise, Fastlane, or personal macOS build servers.

Android, however, provides a more open system where the app being tested has access to the system and other applications under bounded permissions. The Espresso native framework executes under the app pro-

cess using an API that is synchronized, making it possible to develop stable UI tests with little flakiness. Due to Android's design and ability to support environments based on Linux, test automation is easier to scale. Other instruments like UIAutomator, adb, and logcat provide more intrusive access to lower-level test cases like cross-app interactions. Although this variability gives Android an edge in testing capabilities, it also demands careful dependency management, control of the SDK versions, and device fragmentation support.

Approaches to automated and manual testing

Developing and maintaining mobile applications demands a balanced test strategy, where automation and manual testing have complementary roles to play. The choice between the two is not just based on the type of functionality, but also on platform constraints, product maturity, and the velocity of feedback required from each (table 2).

Table 2.

Technical comparison of automated and manual testing in mobile applications [5, 6]

Aspect	Automated testing	Manual testing	Platform notes (iOS / Android)
Execution speed	Fast in CI/CD pipelines; supports parallel runs	Slower, requires human effort and device interaction.	iOS: macOS-only CI runners (XCUITest) Android: faster scaling via Linux agents, Firebase Lab
Coverage	Broad for regressions, flows, API checks	Better for UX, gestures, device-specific behavior.	iOS: stable execution, sandbox limits cross-app coverage Android: more flexible, but fragmented device support
Environment setup	Requires test frameworks, CI tools, signed builds	Needs real or virtual devices, manual setup.	iOS: provisioning profiles, code signing, Xcode Android: Gradle, ADB, fewer restrictions
Tool dependency	Depends on tools like XCUITest, Espresso, Appium	Minimal; tools mainly assist observation, not execution.	iOS: tight Xcode/XCTest integration. Android: Espresso, UIAutomator, adb, logcat support.
Maintenance overhead	High – flakiness, framework updates, synchronization.	Medium – relies on human adaptability.	iOS: stable APIs but strict OS compatibility. Android: SDK/API changes require constant updates.
Subjective feedback	No UX judgment, only logic validation.	Captures look & feel, animation quality, transitions.	iOS: useful for iPad/Mac Catalyst layouts. Android: vital for layout rendering on varied screens.
Error detection type	Logic/data flow, input validation, regressions.	Visual bugs, misalignment, interaction lags.	iOS: fails silently if not handled. Android: device-specific rendering bugs often caught only manually.
Example use case	Validate login, dashboard, API flows.	Test camera behavior during a call or low battery.	iOS: Face ID test under system alert Android: App restart on background event.

Because of the disparity in strategies, tools, and platform features, there is a clear need for a systematic effort distribution in mobile app testing. All tests are not equal when it comes to cost, speed of execution, or intent – some cases are best left to be automated, yet

others require visual examination and manual intervention. To provide a proper representation of how different levels of testing relate to each other in the quality strategy, the following pyramid provides representation of the primary layers of mobile testing and their related functions (fig.3).

Figure 3. Layered structure of mobile testing approaches

This multi-level approach highlights the complementary nature of testing approaches in mobile development. However, prioritization and distribution of levels of testing are fundamentally dependent on platform specifics: the closed iOS platform necessitates intimate integration with Apple's toolset and tight management of the environment, while the more open, more fractured nature of Android allows greater allowance for automated testing but requires greater manual observation for visual and UX confirmation. A good test strategy is never a one-size-fits-all approach – it must be customized to the platform architecture, the product maturity, and the engineering goals, and combining automation and manual tests in a technically aware way.

Comparative assessment of time and resource expenditures for testing in iOS and Android environments

Estimation of testing of mobile applications' cost is based on many factors, including the type of tests, architectural characteristics of the platforms, stability of the UI, and the degree of automation. iOS and Android have different infrastructure and testing methodology requirements, which affect execution time, test stability, and the degree of resources required. The table below presents comparative evaluation of typical values for major types of tests on each platform (table 3).

Table 3.

Comparative metrics of testing time and resource expenditures for iOS and Android platforms [7-9]

Test type	Platform	Avg. test duration	Flakiness (% failing on first run)	Functional coverage (%)	Environment setup time
Unit Tests	iOS	10–30 ms	<1%	70–90%	~30 min
	Android	10–50 ms	<2%	65–85%	~30 min
UI Tests (Native)	iOS (XCUITest)	5–15 s	~3%	60–80%	2–4 h
	Android (Espresso)	6–20 s	~5%	55–75%	1.5–3 h
UI Tests (Appium)	iOS	10–25 s	~7%	50–70%	3–5 h
	Android	12–30 s	~10%	50–70%	3–5 h
E2E Tests	iOS	30–60 s	~5–6%	40–60%	4–6 h
	Android	40–90 s	~6–8%	40–60%	4–6 h
Manual Testing	iOS	2–5 min / scenario	subjective	30–50%	~1 h
	Android	3–10 min / scenario	subjective	30–50%	~1 h

As the figures provided show, iOS testing supports higher test reusability and stability due to the single hardware and software environment. It comes at the expense of increased setup expense and infrastructure complexity, though. Android is more scalable and adaptable in test environments but pays the cost of its high degree of device and OS fragmentation in the form of lower reliability and additional adaptation efforts. So, in choosing a testing approach, aside from considering the test types and level of automation, one must also take into account the platform-specific limitation,

with the goal of achieving stability, cost-effectiveness, and coverage.

Economic and lifecycle implications of platform-specific testing

Post-release maintenance of mobile applications involves recurring costs for bug fixes, test suite updates, OS compatibility, and adaptation to hardware changes. These costs are significantly shaped by platform-specific update models and ecosystem characteristics. iOS offers a centralized and predictable environment, with over 80% of users adopting the latest OS

within months. This enables focused testing across a narrow version range but introduces additional costs due to Apple's strict validation process and frequent API or UI shifts. Each iOS update typically requires 10-25 person-hours for adaptation, while critical bug fixes may take up to 2-3 working days.

Android, in contrast, is highly fragmented, with 5-7 OS versions simultaneously in use and update cycles varying by manufacturer and region. Maintaining Android apps entails broader test coverage, increased regression testing – particularly with custom UI layers – and greater sensitivity to platform variability. Supporting a new Android version can require 20-40 person-hours, and resolving major issues across devices may consume up to 30 hours.

These differences affect the entire product lifecycle – from early design and testing architecture to release cadence, update management, and eventual depreciation. iOS development incurs higher initial investment but benefits from test reuse and controlled maintenance. Android offers flexibility in deployment but shifts costs toward long-term QA and support. Therefore, platform-specific testing constraints must be factored into architectural planning, budgeting, and TCO optimization.

Conclusion

The comparative analysis demonstrates that differences in platform structure, test environments, automation practices, and update patterns have a significant impact on the cost and lifecycle of mobile applications. iOS-centric practices emphasize stability, central authority, and regular release schedules but involve substantial upfront investment in infrastructure and process alignment. On the other hand, Android is less flexible and imposes a lower entry price but higher long-run costs by way of ecosystem fragmentation, manual checking efforts, and complexity in maintaining compatibility between devices and OS versions.

As such, selecting a development and operations strategy for digital offerings will require taking into account the testing-specific characteristics of every platform. CI/CD architecture, resource management, frequency of updates, and behavior after release are all directly affected by testing factors. The inclusion of these factors in planning in the initial phases enables better budgeting, optimization of the TCO, and a more feasible support model throughout the product life cycle.

References:

1. Baresi L., Di Penta M., Quattrocchi G., Tamburri D. A. How have iOS Development Technologies Changed over Time? A Study in Open-Source // Proceedings of the IEEE/ACM 11th International Conference on Mobile Software Engineering and Systems. 2024. P. 33-42. DOI: 10.1145/3647632.3647988
2. Steinböck M., Bleier J., Rainer M., Urban T., Utz C., Lindorfer M. Comparing apples to androids: Discovery, retrieval, and matching of ios and android apps for cross-platform analyses // Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Mining Software Repositories. 2024. P. 348-360.
3. Souha A., Benaddi L., Ouaddi C., Jakimi A. Comparative analysis of mobile application Frameworks: A developer's guide for choosing the right tool // Procedia Computer Science. 2024. Vol. 236. P. 597-604. DOI: 10.1016/j.procs.2024.05.071 EDN: LNNJFO
4. Weichbroth P. Usability testing of mobile applications: A methodological framework // Applied Sciences. 2024. Vol. 14. №. 5. P. 1792. DOI: 10.3390/app14051792 EDN: HLSFBG
5. Swearngin A. Towards automated accessibility report generation for mobile apps // ACM Transactions on Computer-Human Interaction. 2024. Vol. 31. №. 4. P. 1-44. DOI: 10.1145/3674967 EDN: JLNRI
6. Savich A. Integrating digital innovations into business process structures // Professional Bulletin: Economics and Management. 2024. №3/2024. P. 12-16.
7. Rajput Ch., Godiawala S. Bridging The Gap between Android and iOS by Analysing their Incompatibility // International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Communication and Technology. 2022. P. 277-286. DOI:10.48175/IJARST-7792
8. Zhang W., Zhang W., Zhao R. Detecting Concurrent Flaky Test for Android Applications Based on Happens-Before Relationships // Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Computer Information and Big Data Applications. 2024. P. 1187-1191. DOI: 10.1145/3671151.3671358
9. Romano A., Song Z., Grandhi S., Yang W., Wang W. An empirical analysis of UI-based flaky tests // 2021 IEEE/ACM 43rd International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE). IEEE. 2021. P. 1585-1597. DOI: 10.1109/ICSE43902.2021.00141